

STI COLLEGE CALAMBA

STI Academic Center, Barangay Uno, National Highway,
Calamba City, 4027 Laguna

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WASTE TO GROWTH: KNOWING THE IMPACT OF SEED-REWARD RVMs ON WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Authors

Alvaran, Andrei Simon A.

Austria, Ivan Jay B.

Cortez, Jewelyn Kate L.

Grindulo, Jeric Sean M.

Jovito, Sean Andrei M.

Longcop, Nhevea Zhayne C.

Molina, Zyrille B.

Morgado, Jovina Anne B.

Grade 12-Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics, STI College Calamba

Ms. Angeline C. Soriano

Co-author / Research Adviser

STI College Calamba

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ABSTRACT

Title: **WASTE TO GROWTH: KNOWING THE IMPACT OF SEED-REWARD RVMs ON WASTE MANAGEMENT AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY**

Authors: **Alvaran, Andrei Simon A., Austria, Ivan Jay B., Cortez, Jewelyn L., Grindulo, Jeric Sean M., Jovito, Sean Andrei M., Longcop, Nhevea Zhayne C., Molina, Zyrille B., Morgado, Jovina Anne B.**

Co-author/Research Adviser: **Ms. Angeline C. Soriano**

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Reverse Vending Machine (RVM), an early example of automated recycling technology, was first introduced in 1920 under the name "Bottle Return and Handling Machine." This invention provided an innovative solution to tackling the problem of plastic waste. In this study titled "Waste to Growth: Knowing the Impact of Seed-Reward RVMs on Waste Management and Environmental Sustainability," the researchers aim to create a prototype, EcoBloom, focusing on a system where RVMs offer seeds as a reward instead of money. By offering seeds, researchers aim to encourage environmentally positive actions that not only help reduce plastic waste but also support sustainable recycling and encourage an effective implementation towards plastic waste management. The EcoBloom prototype was used for data gathering on selected local officials in Barangay Banlic, Calamba. This study concludes that EcoBloom can help in reducing plastic waste and it can provide the people in the community to gain seeds for their everyday lives and have enough knowledge about planting. EcoBlooms' innovative feature helps in reducing plastic waste, sustaining the environment, and even instill responsibility to one's mind in the sense of recycling, and campaigning green environment to a long-term sustainability.

Keywords: Reverse Vending Machine (RVM), Plastic Bottle Recycling, Sustainable Recycling, Eco-Reward System

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INTRODUCTION

Various types of plastic have been introduced to society for everyday use, manufacture to different products and one Polyethylene Terephthalate, or PET, this is a type of plastic that is commonly used in daily life due to its lightweight and durable characteristics, which make it popular for packaging drinks, food, and various consumer products. (Anon, World Economic Forum, 2022) Plastics can be recycled but they are usually handled poorly and thrown away incorrectly, that contributes to the current global plastic pollution problem, which inspires individuals to adopt recycling can be used to establish a useful tool and help the environment to lessen the pollution that is caused by plastics.

The invention of Hero Alexandria, referred to as the earliest known vending machine that accepts coins in exchange for holy water or alcohol (Bellis, M. 2019). A study by Yadav, P. (2024) indicates that the origin of the reverse vending machine dates back to the 1920s, when the first patent for the empty container return and handling machine was issued to Elmer M. Hones and Sue Walker Vance. Although it was registered in America, the first fully functioning reverse vending machine was created by the Swedish company Wicanders in the late 1950s, and it was further improved by Aage Tveitan in Norway until the first automatic reverse vending machine was made (Lazas, M. 2021). Over the years, many other vending machines have been created and further improved (Kdadmin, 2025). This led to the creation of the fully automatic vending machine created by Simeon Denham, and he earned the first patent no. 706 (Staff, Q. 2022). After the 19th century, concerns over waste and resources emerged as industries tried to improve recycling rate among the public, the theoretical basis for creating the reverse vending machine (Recycle Track Systems. 2023). To this day, RVMs continue to evolve, and further innovations can be introduced to improve their functions (Swinbourne, T. 2024).

Huma Zia et al. (2022) noted that increasing number of plastic bottles discarded is causing a causative concern since they play an important role in filling up landfills as well as overloading the already suffering waste management system, and by recycling the detrimental impact of plastic on the environment can be minimized along with the financial gain that could be achieved, and one way of solving this problem is through the incentive focused RVMs that

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motivate people to participate actively to public plastic waste management. The machine identifies plastic bottles as acceptable deposits and rewards with seeds, and functionality testing revealed superior performance with a suggestion to include labels for improved user direction; test results showed that the respondents highly agreed on the utility of the machine, citing its potential to foster recycling behavior, and the positive feedback highlights its efficiency, ease of use, and the added value of rewarding with seeds, and in general, the device provides an affordable and functional solution to the issue of waste (Judy Ann et al., 2024). As stated by Trinh H., et al (2025) the expand urban population and overpopulated are load with garbage and equipment for treatment, and Vietnam also overlook waste contamination because most dumpsite areas are already overwhelmed, and these were given out in engaging findings on the influence that work on policy implementation, the 2-level conceptual model collected 13 activities to assist the effective implementation, and effective policy implementation build up stronger solid waste management in that scheme goal that change into effort of the society. In the Philippines, approximately 35,580 tons of garbage are generated daily, with each person producing between 0.3 kg to 0.5 kg of waste per day in both rural and urban areas. To address this, they invented the “VendoBin,” a combination of a garbage bin and vending machine, which collects and recycles waste to create new items (Wencel Jean Decay, 2020). The World Bank (Manalad C., et al., 2025) reported in 2012 that 2.9 billion municipal residents generated 0.64 kg of solid waste per person per day, totaling 0.68 billion tons of garbage annually. This figure has since increased, with 3 billion citizens now generating 1.2 kg of waste per person per day, equating to 1.3 billion tons annually. This highlights the need for community education and the establishment of frameworks to contribute to sustainable waste management. The report recommends promoting the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) to achieve sustainable civic waste management.

Based on the study of Mariya et al. (2020). There is a large scope that needs to be improved for the Reverse Vending Machine. That is why the researcher seeks to fill these gaps: Lack of consumer awareness, some consumers are unaware of the type of reverse vending machines and their functions, while others are aware of these things but are unaware of their

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location. Therefore, this case study aims to explore the impact and effect of using a Reverse Vending Machine (RVM) that dispenses seeds as a reward and to explore how a Reverse Vending Machine can help in reducing waste plastic pollution and impact recycling behaviors of local officials. Furthermore, there are studies and constructions of different Reverse Vending Machines; however, seeds as an incentive that aligns with community environmental sustainability has yet been unexplored; so, this study explores how the combination of RVMs and seeds as an incentive impact and affects consumers recycling behaviors.

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METHODOLOGY

In this study, the researchers used a Qualitative Research Method, a method that allowed the researchers to explore the participants' perception and experience (Tenny et al., 2022). Participants' perception about the RVM and how it encourages them to recycle was collected via interviews. Key case study, a detailed examination of a particular project, event, individual, or organization over a defined period (Dhanya, 2024). This allowed the researchers to focus on the complexity and outcomes of using the RVM by examining the RVM during its testing, which provided a more in-depth understanding of what factors need to change for the study to succeed. In order to describe how RVM impacts the recycling behavior of the participants and its effects, Illustrative form of case study was used. A descriptive form which allowed the participants to give information about the case that the researchers are aware of (Hassan, 2024). It was chosen because it can provide valuable insight into how seed-reward reverse vending machines could improve recycling behaviors, reduce plastic pollution to the ecosystem and how a person can be influenced into planting plants or seed to engage in sustainable practices.

Data was gathered by interviewing local officials in Barangay Banlic, Calamba. The sampling method that was used is Purposive Sampling. This sampling allowed the researcher to strategically or purposely select participants based on their specific characteristics or experience. There was a prototype testing and monitoring, where the RVM was placed in the barangay hall of Banlic and was observed for two days to identify possible difficulties and also to assess its overall functionality. After two days, the researchers then select 5-10 local officials, assigned to a specific place, in Brgy. Banlic of Calamba. The researchers presented a PowerPoint presentation to explain how the RVM functions and its process of making. After that, the participants are given time to answer the semi structured interview questionnaires, a type of questionnaire that is used for the participants to freely express their thoughts regarding the prototype. Inductive thematic analysis is a qualitative research method that involves identifying patterns and themes within data without depending on pre-existing theories or frameworks (Byrne, D., 2021). This analysis revealed the motivation and values that drive participants to use RVM in waste management. This type of thematic analysis helped to uncover how seed-reward RVM impacts

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environmental sustainability by looking at different factors that include to gain deeper insights analysis.

This study focuses on exploring the impact of seed rewarding RVMs on waste management and environmental sustainability. The data collection was limited as the researchers are conducting an interview with the local officials of Barangay Banlic, Calamba. One of the limitations of the study is the overall cost, short study period, seed condition or viability, users' awareness and participation, misuse, and location dependency. For its delimitation, the machine only accepts specific types and sizes of plastic bottles and is designed for individuals who have an interest in planting. During the data collection process, the participants were informed that their participation was completely voluntary, and their responses remain confidential. Only required personal data was collected, and all data was anonymized and securely stored. Used solely for research purposes to ensure protection of data and maintaining confidentiality. No personal information is stored beyond the duration of the study.

Figure 1. Stages of Prototype Development

The figure above shows how the researchers started with their initial plan in constructing the RVM. Making the prototype Ecobloom was quite a challenge for the researchers. Due to the lack of knowledge of making machines like reverse vending machines,

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the researchers bought some wrong materials, shown in figure 2 is the buying and selection of materials. To ensure that the machine will function, the researchers seek help from a professional engineer. After that while the professional engineer was fixing the wiring and connections, the researchers made the outer casing of the whole RVM. Next, in picture 4 is the prototype testing, here the researchers checked its function. Lastly, putting every piece together and designing the RVM is important. For improvements, the researchers installed a wheel, changed the packaging of the seeds into parchment paper, some components were also replaced and added for better usage like the buck converter, and instructions were provided to guide users. With these the researchers were able to make an RVM.

MATERIAL/S	IMAGE	FUNCTION
Arduino Mega 2560		A motherboard designed for projects that uses memory or RAM
DC Gear Motor 12v		Gear motor which controls precise and smooth motion.
Connecting wires		Components that give an electric flow to a device which allow to function
Capacitive Proximity Sensor		A device which allows to detect a presence of object without physical contact
Inductive Proximity Sensor		It detects a metallic object without physical contact.
Ultrasonic Sensor		Releases a high frequency sound wave and measures the returning time of the reflected wave, allowing it to detect without contact.
Power Supply 12V		It converts an electric into a voltage

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Capacitor 12V		It stores electric energy by collecting two different dielectrics.
Resistors (64k and 100k)		It limits the electrical flow in a circuit.
4-channel relay		Control four different high-powered circuits with a single low-power control signal.
LCD		Shows the text message
Buck converter		It reduces a high input voltage to a lower output voltage.

Table 1. List of Materials

Listed in table 1 are the materials that the researchers used for the RVM. Each has different functions that help with the prototype's objectives. With it the detection and reward process has become easier.

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RESULTS

Table 2

Participant Insights in Stages of Development of EcoBloom

Actual Response	Theme	Description
<p>“It helps in reducing plastic waste especially, plastic bottles.” (P2)</p>	<p>Helpful in Plastic Waste Reduction</p>	<p>EcoBloom machine's advantage is that it helps reduce plastic waste, specifically plastic bottles.</p>
<p>“So sa tingin ko yung isang magandang advantage nun, nung ginagawa nyo yun, is yung malessening yung mga kalat natin dito.” (BOE2)</p>		
<p>“Makakatulong siya mabawasan ang mga basura at matulungan natin ang environmental, example ay pag rerecycle” (BOE1)</p>		
<p>“Ayan, kagaya ng sabi mo, siguro yung pagiging maselan nyo din sa mga bagay na gagamitin nyo. Kasi nga gaya ng sabi mo, hindi siya mabubuo kung basta-basta lang din yung materials na gagamitin. Siguro ano na lang, yung bang mga tawag dito, kung meron mang mga bagay siguro, kayo yung nakakaalam nun eh, kasi kayo din yung mismong gumawa nun.” (BOE2)</p>	<p>Good Selection of Materials</p>	<p>In the development process of a prototype like EcoBloom, material selection is one of the things we should consider because of its price and every material has its own function. Since it can contribute to its overall success.</p>
<p>“Una-una, kasi STEM student din naman ako, gets na gets ko yung ganyan kasi may robotics din kami. Una-una yung programming, napakahirap niyan. Yung mga materials na such as the bottles, the circuitry, the breadboard, the display, mga sensor na hindi naman talaga maikakaila na mahal talaga siya, may presyo talaga siya. So yun talaga yung pinaka-problem na nakita.” (BOE3)</p>		

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Table 2 represents the stages of development of EcoBloom in planning its production. The table displays the theme generated from the participants' feedback. Plastic Waste Reduction and Material Selection Consciousness are the major themes that the researchers generated from the participants' answers. One of the advantages that the EcoBloom machine contributes is that it has the ability to help reduce plastic waste in a community or place. To ensure the success of making an RVM machine, carefully selecting the materials that will be used is important.

In accordance with Huma Zia (2022), Through RVMs provision of a motivation for the proper disposal, these machines reduce the levels of plastic waste that find their way into the landfills and oceans. There are RVMs that apply classification using deep learning to recognize and sort plastic bottles effectively, smoothening the process of recycling as well as efficiency.

RVMs in these countries have largely improved waste management, indicating technology-based solutions could play a critical role in helping achieve environmental sustainability. Selecting a material for a product prototype plays a crucial role in meeting set design criteria, as well as ensuring its operation in real-life scenarios, as materials provide various challenges in terms of flexibility, durability, and costs. Thorough material selection makes sure through evaluation can prove accurate predictions concerning the functioning of the product. (Fatima et al., 2022).

Table 3
Participant Insights in the Performance of EcoBloom

Actual Response	Theme	Description
<p>“May possible na masira gawa po ng ano, marami pong gagamit.” (P2)</p> <p>“Uhm sa schools po, pwede pong masira yung machine kasi madami pong nagamit neto” (P1)</p> <p>“Siguro kung sa materials na pag-uusapan natin, limit lang din. Kasi kung hindi naman siya talagang yung sabihin natin na talagang kaya niya ng mga pang-heavy na mga gamit, lalo na kung napakadami na. Katulad dito sa barangay namin, kung titignan nyo yung mga basura namin dito, napakadami. So kung titignan nyo, siguro para sa akin na, hindi pa, kung baga hindi pa nyo na kuha yung pinaka-limit ng pinaka mga basura.” (BOE2)</p>	<p>Decrease Durability Under High Usage</p>	<p>If the EcoBloom machine were used by many and it reached its maximum capacity, it has the tendency to malfunction or to cause its breakage.</p>

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<p>“Pwede pong masira yung machine kasi po yung case neto is kahoy po” (P1)</p>	<p align="center">Fragile Casing Hinders Performance</p>	<p>The EcoBlooms performance can be affected by hazardous factors. The material used needs to be improved to ensure that it can perform and function properly.</p>
<p>“Pwede po siyang masira, for example po umulan, pwede po siyang mabas or mabasa po iyung components po sa loob.” (P2)</p>		
<p>“Ah, okay. So, assuming na gawa naman talaga sa kahoy, which is a biodegradable resource sa ating mundo, sa tingin ko hindi niya maha-handle yung hazardous factors such as the dustings of wind, the rainstorms, the thunderstorms, lalo lalo na yung mababasa siya dahil magkakaroon siya ng oxidation, or hindi ko sure na oxidation, pero magkakaroon siya ng degradation tulad ng pagkatagkaroon ng lumot, magiging marupok yung kahoy. Pero kung gawa sa steel yan, kung meron talagang enough resources, diba, pwede pwede yan.” (BOE3)</p>		

Table 3 presents the themes that emerged from the participants' feedback and answers.

The EcoBlooms performance depends on the materials that will be used to ensure that it can last long enough, its durability, and function properly.

The study of Hussain (2022) highlighted the development of a low cost lightweight RVM, emphasizing the importance of choosing materials to provide durability without sacrificing portability. Materials selection is important to make sure the durability of the prototype is ensured.

Table 4

Participant Insights in the Features of EcoBloom

Actual Response	Theme	Description
<p>“Actually, sa pinakita niyong video demonstration, sobrang dali. Magiging accessible siya. Kasi considering sa height, yun nga yung una kong napansin, yung height ng prototype nyo, it is accessible even the people in wheelchair can use that prototype. Yun talaga ang nakita ko. Kaya, galing.” (BOE3)</p>	<p align="center">Accessible and User Friendly</p>	<p>EcoBloom’s structure contributes to the accessibility and ease of use. The design caters to a broad range of users by considering factors such as height, ensuring that individuals with varying abilities can interact with it comfortably, ensures that the product can be used by people of all ages and physical conditions, showcasing a thoughtful approach to universal usability and user-centered design. These features contribute to its user friendliness.</p>
<p>“oo, madalin lang. Kase kahit bata pwede syang gamitin, kapag nakita nila yung instruction. Ipapasok mo lang yung bottle tapos may lalabas na, kukunin mo nalang yung reward” (BOE1)</p>		

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<p>“Aba oo, talagang user-friendly siya, kasi hindi mo kailangang mag-isip ng malalim kung paano gagamitin kasi madali lang tapos eco-friendly rin kasi hindi ko gagamitan ng kung ano-anong chemical.” (P3)</p>		
<p>“Uhm It depends kasi yung ibang tao po hindi po naeenganyo sa pagtatanim while yung iba po is hilig po nila.” (P2)</p>	<p align="center">Motivating and Engaging Incentives</p>	<p>The Ecoloom’s incentives engagement can vary based on the users' preferences. While some may find it motivating and useful because it aligns with their interests, others may find it unhelpful due to differing preferences.</p>
<p>“Sa case na yan, hindi ko rin masasabi kung magiging interested pa sila or hindi. Dahil depende naman sa location na ipoperson nyo yan. Such as di, kung halimbawa ilalagay nyo yan sa isang agricultural barangay or agricultural area, mapapakita nyo talaga na magiging impactful yan. Pero kung ilalagay nyo yan sa mga polluted areas, tulad ng Manila, na puro building, puro skyscraper, sa tingin ko hindi yun ganun mapapansin.” (BOE3)</p>		

Table 4 presents themes that emerge from participants’ answers. The features of EcoBloom are accessible to people with age and physical condition, additional are children in terms of their height. Its features are user friendly, specifically the instructions it has. The seed rewards can be engaging to some who have the interest and habit of planting while others may not; it depends on their preferences.

A likely study of Baribad et. al, (2024), It also features being user-friendly machine that could have a potential impact in promoting recycling practices. It minimizes confusion and complexity, making it more accessible to all users.

Table 5

Participant Insights in EcoBloom’s Influence in User Engagement and Satisfaction

Actual Response	Theme	Description
<p>“Oo, syempre. Imbis na itatapon nila yung basura sa labas, itatapon nalang nila sa EcoBloom. Makakapag-recycle tayo, mawawalan tayo ng mga basura pati mga kalat.” (BOE1)</p>	<p align="center">Engaging to Recycling towards to Cleaner Environment</p>	<p>EcoBloom strives to make recycling a habit, to help reduce plastic waste and create an even more sustainable community.</p>
<p>“Hindi na magiging pakalat-kalat iyung mga bote sa paligid. Dahil nakatulong</p>		

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ka na sa kapaligiran tapos nakatulong ka pa sa sarili mo.” (P3)		
"Magpapakita naman yan ng satisfaction sa mga tao sa pamamagitan ng recycling. Sa pamamagitan naman yan ng pagkakaroon ng mindset nila na mayroong pa talagang way para mag-recycle ang ating mundo. Pero mas pinapakita na yan dahil mayroon kayong in exchange for something that's way more better na magbibigay kayo ng agricultural products.” (BOE3)	Consumable Incentives as a Motivation	The machine itself offers a physical reward such as seeds. It makes the recycling process feel more rewarding as it makes the feelings good and those incentives keep people from continuing recycling.
“Dito kasi magiging interasado na sila kung mayroong din silang makukubang reward.” (BOE2)		

Table 5 gives an insight into EcoBloom’s influence on user engagement and satisfaction. The theme of the table implies that engagement is seen when an individual feels rewarded, and seeing a direct benefit from the action itself tends to commit to a participation towards a cleaner environment.

As the study proposed by Zhang et al. (2024), the ease of use and perceived value of recycling vending machines (RVMs), including their economic, social, and environmental advantages, are crucial in building the public trust and aligning in encouraging participation. EcoBloom’s theme perceived that incentives or rewards are a must toward the trust of the people to use the reverse vending machine.

Table 6

Participant Insights in EcoBloom’s Impact in terms of Environmental Sustainability, Waste Management, or Even Community Engagement

Actual Response	Theme	Description
"Oo, malaking advantage sa'tin, kasi tulad niyan, imbis nakakalat sa iba't ibang lugar yung mga basura, ilalagay niya nalang don, automatic nakapag-recycle na. Malaking tulong sa'tin.” (BOE4)	Maximizing Waste Reduction for a Sustainable Future	Recycling through EcoBloom does not stop in reducing plastic waste, but it also contributes to lessening the demand for new plastic production. This statement implies how EcoBloom reduces the plastic waste in certain places by offering a sustainable solution. This initiative not only helps

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<p>"Oo, hindi na magiging pakalat-kalat yung mga bote sa paligid. Dahil nakatulong ka na sa kapaligiran, tapos nakatulong ka pa sa sarili mo. At yun nga, sabi ko, sa nangyayari sa lugar natin, yung mga plastic waste, in the future, hindi na makakaapekto sa ating lugar at sa paligid."(U3)</p>		<p>the environment cleaner but also engages the community to have a drive to a long-term reduction of plastic waste.</p>
<p>"Makakatulong pa ito sa mga kabataan, sa mga tao, at hindi na magiging problema yung mga bote na nakakalat lang sa mga lugar. At least, sa EcoBloom, may instant buto ka na pagkatapos mong ilagay yung plastic bottles." (U3)</p>	<p align="center">Empowering Youth and Community Engagement through the EcoBloom</p>	<p>EcoBloom’s not only promotes recycling but also helps to instill a mindset of responsibility and service, to engage the youth and positively influence local government to create a collaboration towards the reverse vending machine.</p>
<p>"Ako kasi, bilang SK Chairman dito sa ating barangay, nakita ko siya na effective talaga siya. Malaki yung maitutulong niya para sa akin, lalo na sa mga kabataan. Kasi hindi naman lahat ng kabataan ay talagang gustong gumawa ng ganyan. Natutuwa nga ako sa inyo kasi naisip niyo yung bagay na kung baga, meron kayong kaisipan na makatulong sa community, hindi lang sa sarili ninyo. Kasi sa iba, pag mga nagre-research sila, more on about sa sarili din nila, kung ano yung mapapakinabangan nila. Pero yung sa inyo, makikita mo yung care ninyo sa community, hindi lang sa pansarili ninyo. Kaya para sa akin, bilang isang government official, napaka-effective niya talaga, lalo na dito sa barangay namin." (BOE2)</p>		
<p>"As a government official, makikita talaga namin yan na isang very reliable and very effective mitigation of the agricultural improvement of our community. Lalo lalo na napakarami rito palayan, napakarami dito taniman, napakarami rito kailangan ng mga ganyang materials para makapagsimula sa agricultural investment." (BOE3)</p>	<p align="center">Effective Tool for Improving Agriculture Aspect in Local Community</p>	<p>EcoBloom can be a way of improving the agricultural aspect in a certain community. Through this project, opportunities can be created for those in need.</p>
<p>"Bilang punong barangay, talagang magandang tulong sa atin yan, lalo na sa mga walang trabaho, magkakaroon sila ng trabaho sa pagtatanim, yung tulong ng project nyo ay malaking tulong sa mamamayan." (BOE1)</p>		

Table 6 outlines the themes that engaged in EcoBloom impact in terms of various social involvement into the society. EcoBloom is not limited to recycling but instilling a mindset of responsibility and service to positively engage people to interact with the machine.

As it is connected to the study of Angelovska-Dichovska, et al. (2023), it involves looking at community attitudes, engagement with recycling programs, and the perceived effectiveness of these machines in reducing waste.

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DISCUSSION

Several themes emerged from participants' responses: **Helpful in Plastic Waste Reduction and Selection of Good Materials**. For the performance are **Decrease Durability under High Usage and Fragile Casing Hinders Performance, Accessible and User Friendly and Motivating and Engaging Incentives** for its features, **Engaging to Recycling towards to Cleaner Environment and Consumable Incentives as a Motivation** in its influence. And lastly **Maximizing Waste Reduction for a Sustainable Future, Empowering Youth and Community Engagement through the EcoBloom, and Effective Tool for Improving Agriculture Aspect in Local Community** about its impact.

The first theme discusses the prototypes' main reason for development, to reduce the amount of plastic waste. The success of the development of ecobloom relies on the selection of good materials, which is the second theme, that can also be a factor for its performance, like the casing. The seed reward can be motivating for some who are interested in it, while others might find it useless. EcoBlooms' existence helped people to become aware of the function of such machines. EcoBloom has a great factor in reducing plastic waste and engaging people to recycle. The materials used for the construction contribute to the prototype's durability and function. Poor quality of materials can result in breakage and malfunction.

EcoBloom machines help people to reduce waste and with this study, consumers become aware that such machines exist to help with plastic waste. In comparison to other reverse vending machines, that has incentives like coins, snacks, beverages, and many more. EcoBloom is a machine that can contribute to our environment as it dispenses seed rewards in exchange for plastic waste bottles. Additionally, compared to other RVMs, EcoBlooms' size is easier and more accessible to other people, especially kids and those who have physical disabilities. The rewards are not only helpful in our ecosystem but also the machine itself as it can help reduce plastic waste. This study has only a short testing duration and construction, limited financial resources as the researchers are still young students, and the availability of materials which limit the researcher's capability to understand more and to assess the prototype.

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Based on the result of this study, the findings revealed significant improvement in the Ecoblooms performance and engagement compared to what the researchers used. Considering the findings, it is recommended that future researchers use different materials for the prototypes' durability and longer use for consumers. The following specific recommendations are provided:

1. Engineers and developers may use metal as the reverse vending machine's casing to ensure durability and prevent breakage. Technologists and designers may implement an image scanning sensor, such as Raspberry Pi or a laser scanner, to improve plastic bottle detection accuracy.
2. Researchers and innovators may integrate weighing sensors to classify and differentiate specific types of plastic bottles more precisely.
3. Environmental advocates and policymakers may utilize the findings of this study to help reduce plastic waste, support farmers/locals in acquiring seeds, and promote knowledge about planting.
4. Educators and sustainability leaders may leverage EcoBlooms' innovative features to encourage recycling, foster environmental responsibility, and advocate for long-term sustainability through green initiatives.

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